

Maximization Of Arrangements and Quantum Bound States

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The Maxwell-Boltzmann MB distribution is often derived by maximizing the number of possible arrangements of particles with different energies subject to the constraint of a fixed number of particles and fixed energy. Using the canonical approximation that only average energy is conserved and using Stirling's approximation for large number factorials leads to the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution. The \ln of total number of arrangements using Stirling's approximation is linked to a math form called Shannon's entropy i.e. $-\sum_i f(e_i) \ln(f(e_i))$.

Interestingly this same MB result may be obtained through reaction balance which makes no use of the idea of arrangements or entropy or maximization. It is concerned with including all possible physical reactions (for example two body reactions between all energy particles) subject to conservation of energy. In this sense it deals directly with the dynamics of the problem while the arrangement approach does not. The dynamical approach considers all possible reactions with notions of independence or lack of information and ensures the system remains unchanged. Why are they the same? We argue that it is because the "recipe" for the probability of two body reactions namely $n(e_1)n(e_2)$ is of the same form as the leading factor of $n(e_1)!n(e_2)!$.

In the case of quantum mechanics one may apply the dynamical approach to obtain the time-independent Schrodinger equation. In such a case one does not need to think in terms of "maximizing" any quantity although one considers all possible reactions with a potential $V(x)$. $a(p)$ factors in $W(x) = \text{wavefunction} = \sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$ are interrelated, but retain their identity after all possible interactions occur. This we argue is the idea for the eigenvalue equation.

At the same time, Shannon's entropy, which is directly linked to the notion of arrangements, is applied to a bound state and possibly linked to thermodynamics i.e. $dE = TdS - PdV$ which may be applied to an adiabatic expansion. Shannon's entropy is created from existing probabilities in this case which do not arise from explicitly maximizing entropy subject to constraints as the probabilities follow directly from the Schrodinger equation. One might ask why Shannon's entropy has any relevance if it is the dynamics which determines the value of $W(x)$ and $a(p)$. It seems, however, that one may knock out a particle in a state p with probability $P(p) = a^*(p)a(p)$ or find a particle at x with probability $P(x) = W^*(x)W(x)$. These are classical type probabilities linked to the quantum dynamical probabilities $a(p)$ and $W(x)$. It seems Shannon's entropy is only applied to $P(x)$ and $P(p)$ or a product $P(x)P(p)$ which may give it physical meaning in a quantum bound state.

We examine these ideas in this note.

Maximization of Arrangements

Arrangements are static yet interactions are needed to change a system from one to another. Thus we argue that dynamics are key. For an ideal gas, however, it seems the constraints in the system allow for all possible arrangements subject to constant particle number and average

energy. Average energy means that the canonical and not microcanonical approach is used. N particles may have $n(e_i)$ particles with energy e_i . No e_i is excluded. The number of arrangements is:

$$N! / \text{Product over } i \ n(e_i)! \quad \text{Taking "ln" yields } \ln(N!) - \text{Sum over } i \ \ln\{n(e_i)!\} \quad ((1))$$

If one uses Stirling's approximation (i.e. assuming all $n(e_i)$ are very large, then:

$$\ln(\# \text{ arrangements}) = C_1 - \text{Sum over } i \ n(e_i) \ln(e_i) \quad ((2)) \text{ dropping } n(e_i) \text{ terms.}$$

-Sum over $i \ n(e_i) \ln(e_i)$ is called Shannon's entropy and may be maximized subject to the constraints $\text{Sum over } i \ n(e_i) = N$ and $\text{Sum over } i \ e_i n(e_i) = E_{\text{ave}}$. This yields that Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution:

$$P(e_i) = C_2 \exp(-e_i/T) \quad ((3))$$

An alternative approach is to consider ((1)), the number of arrangements, together with a single two body collision as the source of a change in $n(e)$ and $n(e_1-e)$ for two chosen values e and e_1 . Energy and particle number are kept constant so the number of arrangements should be the same to first order. From the factorials (without using Stirling's approximation) one loses one e and one e_1-e and gains an e_2 and e_1-e_2 with e and e_2 being less than e_1 . Thus:

$$n(e_1-e)n(e) = \{n(e_2)+1\} \{n(e-e_2)+1\} \quad ((4))$$

If one keeps e_1 fixed and chooses $e_2=e+de$ then infinitesimal terms give, assuming terms with e and e_1 are independent:

$dn/de = C\{n(e) + 1\}$ but $n(e) \gg 1$ so $n(e)$ is proportional to $\exp(-Ce)$ with the minus chosen so $n(e)$ goes to zero as e becomes very large.

Alternatively, one may examine ((4)) and argue that one may choose e_3 instead of e on the LHS. Any e_3 less than e is acceptable and all should yield the same value. Thus:

$$n(e_1-e)n(e) = n(e_1-e_2)n(e_2) \quad ((5)) \quad \text{This suggests that } n \text{ is a power of } e \text{ so } \exp(-e/T) \text{ is a solution.}$$

In other words there is a loss of information as any pairs e and e_1-e are acceptable as long as $e < e_1$.

((5)), however, is exactly the condition for the probability of two body scattering. Thus a reaction balance approach and maximization of arrangements are the same for the ideal gas situation. In other words, one does not have to think in terms of maximization or entropy at all, but take into account all possible reactions which conserve energy and particle number. Thus for elastic two body scattering reaction balance yields:

$$n(e_1)n(e_2) = n(e_3)n(e_4) \text{ and } e_1+e_2 = e_3 + e_4 \quad ((6))$$

Taking In of the first equation and equating to the second yields the MB distribution. The point we wish to make is that considering dynamics (i.e. reaction balance) and paying no heed to maximization or entropy allows one to solve for the MB distribution. (Maximization is implicitly contained in the approach without one being aware, it seems.) The reason we emphasize this dynamical approach is that it seems to apply to quantum mechanical bound states.

Quantum Mechanics

Quantum mechanics is a statistical theory so an immediate question arises: Why does one not maximize entropy subject to constraints? In the Maxwell-Boltzmann case it happens that a dynamical reaction balance is the same as maximizing entropy, but that need not be the case. We argue that the dynamics determine the equilibrium and that perhaps the rule to use is to consider all physically possible interactions which leave the distribution unchanged. This is the approach used in $n(e_1)n(e_2)=n(e_3)n(e_4)$ with $e_1+e_2 = e_3+e_4$.

For quantum bound states, collisions with the potential are key. We start with the a priori assumption of dynamical probabilities $\exp(ipx)$ for free particles. We consider an ensemble $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$. For equilibrium, interactions (with $V(x)$) should leave the $W(x)$ unchanged. $V(x)$, however, is in the form of energy, so if one tries to write the interactions in terms of conservation of energy then:

$$V(x)W(x) = \text{Sum over } k \ V_k \exp(ikx) * \text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \exp(ipx) \quad ((7))$$

There is a mixing of $\exp(ipx)$'s with $\exp(ikx)$'s just as in an ideal gas. In this case, however, two particles with new energies are not produced rather a single $a(p)$ is. Furthermore, one cannot follow particles in time and so one cannot consider one collision of a p_1 with a k_1 separately from a p_2 with a k_2 . As a result, one has:

$$p^2/2m \ a(p) + \text{Sum over } p \ V_k \ a(p-k) = E \ a(p) \quad ((8))$$

The distribution $W(x)$ remains the same by having an eigenvalue equation. ((8)) may be rewritten as:

$$-1/2m \ d^2W/dx^2 + V(x)W(x) = E W(x) \quad ((9)) \text{ which is the time-independent Schrodinger equation.}$$

((9)) allows one to solve for $W(x)$ and $a(p)$ without any notion of maximization although implicitly there may be maximization. One focuses instead on the dynamics of the problem. This immediately leads to the question: Is there any need for Shannon's entropy for a bound quantum state?

Shannon's Entropy

In a quantum bound state, one has two sets of probabilities:

$a(p)$ and $W(x)$ which are linked to dynamics i.e. $\exp(ipx)$ a free particle dynamical probability and are obtained by considering collisions with $V(x)$ and conservation of average energy i.e. dynamics and:

$P(p)=a^*(p)a(p)$ and $P(x)=W^*(x)W(x)$ which are classical types of probabilities, the same which appear in classical physics.

As a result, one might try to create a Shannon's entropy using $P(p)$ or $P(x)$ as done in the literature (1) i.e. $S_x = - \int dx P(x) \ln(P(x))$ and $S_p = - \int dp P(p) \ln(P(p))$ 1-D ((10))

In previous notes, we have suggested using $\text{Probability} = W(x)a(p) \exp(ipx)$ leading to $S = S_p + S_x$.

If one considers that a particle knocked out of a bound state has a probability of $P(p)$ of having momentum p and that there is a probability of finding a particle at x of $P(x)$ then it seems Shannon's forms of S_x and S_p are linked to various arrangements i.e. ensemble results. One cannot, however, apply maximization of entropy subject to any simple constraints to find $a(p)$ and $W(x)$.

Nevertheless $S_p + S_x$ is a description of the system using the classical probabilities $P(x)$ and $P(p)$.

One may note that for a particle in a box or an oscillator $S = S_p + S_x$ has the property that if one changes L the box length or k the spring constant adiabatically, then S remains a constant. Furthermore $S_p + S_x$ indicates there is probability within the system which changes with overall energy E_n . This is similar to the idea of TdS in thermodynamics. For a particle in a box with infinite walls E_n goes as n^2 , while S_x is independent of n , but S_p depends on n in a complicated manner, which approaches a constant as n goes to infinite (1).

Conclusion

In conclusion, for an ideal gas one may maximize the \ln of the number of arrangements subject to a constraint on the number of particles and average energy to obtain the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution. This maximization yields the identical result as reaction balance. In this note we try to show this is due to the reaction form $n(e_1)n(e_2) = n(e_3)n(e_4)$ where $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$ keeping the factorial arrangement expression constant. We argue, however, that equilibrium seems to be established through dynamics i.e. interactions and argue that it may be best to consider all possible interaction-collisions which do not violate constraints. This approach may be applied to a quantum bound state assuming a dynamic probability for free particles of $\exp(ipx)$. An ensemble $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ interacts with $V(x)$, but one cannot simply pull out the impulse collisions from the energy (i.e. one writes $V(x) = \sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$). Thus writing an expression which involves interactions also requires using

conservation of average energy E_n and leads to an eigenvalue equation because the interactions return the ensemble multiplied by E_n . In such a calculation, as in action-reaction balance there is no explicit maximization process, but one obtains $a(p)$ and $W(x)$.

From these one may calculate $P(p) = a^*(p)a(p)$ and $P(x) = W^*(x)W(x)$ which have experimental meaning. Thus we argue Shannon's entropy $S = S_p + S_x$ should also have meaning. For different experiments one may use S_p or S_x alone. We note that $S_p + S_x$ is independent of L (box length) for an infinite well or k for an oscillator if the system is changed adiabatically. Thus Shannon's entropy may have some link to thermodynamic entropy, although the underlying dynamic probabilities $a(p)$ and $W(x)$ are calculated through considering all possible interactions consistent with physical constraints, not by using Shannon's entropy or explicit maximization we argue.

References

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Particle_in_a_box